

CONCEPT AND TYPES OF INNOVATION IN SOCIO-ECONOMIC ACTIVITY

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Abstract: Innovation is the result of activity or activity that involves the use of new knowledge embodied in new technologies, know-how, new combinations of production factors, as well as the creation of new products capable of performing new tasks with high market potential or eliminating the negative consequences of destructive processes. That is, innovations can be considered as the result of the transformation of ideas, researches, developments, new or perfect scientific-technical or socio-economic decisions.

Keywords: intellectual activity, Innovation model, climate resources, innovation support

The development of scientific views on innovation has its own history and has been consistently studied by representatives of the classical and neoclassical schools. The famous English economist Adam Smith (1729-1790), a representative of the classical economic school, noted that regulation of economic relations and ensuring the balance between supply and demand is not only a market system, but also an organizational mechanism of capitalism, which satisfies increasing needs by lowering prices and improving quality, as well as transitioning to new technologies, i.e. competition that effectively implements this with the help of innovations.

If we take into account that enterprises use innovation as a practical factor in the struggle for consumption to ensure economic growth, this doctrine of Adam Smith remains relevant today.

Despite the fact that the practice of innovation has existed for thousands of

years, the scientific study of innovation began only in the 20th century. Russian economist N.D. Kondratev made a great contribution to the development of the theory of the innovative way of improving the economy. He mentioned innovation as one of the causes of periodicity.

American economist and sociologist Joseph Alois Schumpeter, like Kondratev, made a great contribution to increasing the role of innovation in the economy. In his work entitled "Theory of Economic Development", he considered innovations as the main conditions for the development of the economy and society. Schumpeter created the "innovative theory of entrepreneurship" and highly valued the role of the innovator-entrepreneur in economic development, including the term "innovation" among scientific terms in 1911. It envisages a combination of new scientific and technical factors stimulated by the spirit of entrepreneurship in the following five changes:

1. Use of new techniques, new technological processes or new market supply of production.
2. Introducing a product with new features.
3. Use of new raw materials.
4. Changes in the organization of production and its material and technical support.
5. Emergence of new sales markets.

Therefore, according to Schumpeter, the role of entrepreneurs is to reform and revolutionize production by using inventions to produce new goods and to produce old goods in new ways, by opening up new sources of raw materials and materials or new markets, and by reorganizing the industry. In that period, the beginning of the construction of railways, the production of electricity, the development of the automobile industry, etc. can be a vivid example of entrepreneurs' desire to profit from innovations.

Simon Kuznets's Nobel Prize-winning lecture is devoted to the problem of

interdependence of innovation and economic growth. It mentions a number of new approaches to the theory of innovation that develop Joseph Schumpeter's ideas

firstly, Simon Kuznets introduced the concept of "period" which forms the basis of the transition from one historical period to another.

Secondly, the revolutionary acceleration of economic growth in the industrial era, according to him, the rapid development of science related to periodic innovation became a new source of growth.

Understanding the content and essence of innovations based on the views of economists, it can be said that an innovative economy is an economy capable of effectively using any innovations useful for society (patents, licenses, know-how, acquired or personal innovations, new technologies, etc.).

The introduction of news is becoming more and more important in economic life. In today's rapidly changing environment, companies need to be progressive and successfully implement innovations along with technical changes. The introduction of news should be based on the initial evaluation of the system. In order to create a methodological basis for such an assessment, first of all, it is necessary to determine the set of factors that affect the total innovation process and determine the effectiveness of one or another innovation.

Two directions of emergence of innovations

- Market need, that is, the demand for a certain product or service. in other words, it is a response to market needs or a marketing option. For example, such changes may include changes that help reduce production costs or give the product a more "merchandise" appearance.

- "Discovery" (intellectual activity) is the intellectual activity of a person to create a new product aimed at satisfying a demand that does not exist in the market. in other words, it is the activity of creating a new market

Innovative type of development (ingl. Innovation model of development) - emphasis on new advanced technologies in social production, production of products

based on high technologies, adoption of advanced organizational and management decisions in micro- and macro-economic processes - technopark, technopolis, policy of using low-energy technologies, intellectualization of production activities, softening and servicing of the economy.

Innovation management is a relatively new concept for the economy of Uzbekistan, which covers the main aspects of the management processes of scientific and technical progress and the introduction of scientific and technical achievements into production.

Innovation is the process of managing the development of existing systems, in which an innovative product is brought to the stage of practical application and ensures market success.

The assessment of the competitiveness of countries shows that the main strategy for the development of enterprises is the implementation of management policies based on the following principles:

- rational use of natural and climate resources;
- proper use of accumulated wealth;
- active attraction of investments;
- innovation support.

One of the most important practical tasks of innovation management is the formation of an effective system of management of innovation processes, and it involves the following:

- development of the appropriate theoretical base of innovative management;
- justification of methods of solving existing problems in the field of innovative management;
- development of methods for evaluating the effectiveness of innovative processes and influencing them.

The innovation process can be divided into three logical forms: simple intra-enterprise (natural), simple inter-enterprise (commodity) and extended.

Diffusion of innovation is a process by means of which innovation is transmitted over time between members of a social system through communication channels. Innovations are ideas, objects, technologies, etc. that are new to the relevant business entity. can serve. In other words, diffusion is the spreading of an innovation once mastered and used in new conditions or places.

Researching the uniqueness of new products, it is possible to express a number of limitations on the organization of management of innovative activities:

- the complexity of establishing a universal form of organizing the development of scientific and technical development;
- quality difference between innovative and everyday production process;
- the need to use different management systems at different stages of the innovation process;

Innovation is the result of introducing innovation in order to change the object of management and obtain economic, social, ecological, scientific-technical and other types of benefits.

Innovative activity is directed to the application of scientific, scientific and technical results and intellectual potential in order to obtain a new or improved product (service, process, method). The main components of innovative activity in market conditions are innovations, investments and innovations that make up the sphere of innovative activity.

By innovative process, we understand the process of turning scientific knowledge into innovation, that is, such a sequence of events in which innovation turns from an idea into a final product.

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